

Attachment to the Study Report:

Script used for participatory mapping on Ovalau Island, Fiji, in 2025

Step 1- Ice-breaker with a Mental Map (see in report 2.3)

- Draw a map of your Vanua (*using pencils and colored pencils, on A4 paper*)
- Please add to your map the names of the places you use the most in your Vanua?

Step 2 – Guiding tasks and questions for the Participatory Map sessions (see in report 2.4)

Introduction:

- Let's take the time to have a look at the map...
- Can you identify the places you drew before [in the mental map]? (*using stars-stickers*)

First task/set of questions: Fishing

- Please circle your favorite or main fishing grounds and add their names (*using the yellow pen*)
- What are your fishing practices in these fishing grounds? (*using square sticky notes*)

Second task/set of questions: Names of the reef passages

- Please name on the map all the reef passages you know (*using arrow sticky notes*)
- Identify on the map other human activities in or around these reef passages (*using colored dots, with a key on an A4 paper*)

Third task/set of questions: Governance/Management/Conservation

- Are there any tabu areas for fishing in place? Can you draw the boundaries? (*using the orange pen*)
- Are there sacred or culturally important areas? (*using the white pen*)
- Can you locate turtle nesting sites on the map? (*using larger orange dots*)
- Which places or areas would you like to keep for future generations? Why? (*using white dotted lines*)
- Where is the reef degraded or unhealthy? (*using red dots*)

Step 3 – Get consent from the participants to use the information shared during the mapping sessions

Is it OK if we share some of the information from this workshop outside this community?
Or is there any information from this workshop you do not want us to share outside this community?